

Fourier Transform Infrared Kinetic Study of the Thermal Decomposition of Tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione and Dimethylketene[†]

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The vapor phase thermolysis of tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione (TMCBD) has been studied in the temperature range 383-430° by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The first order decay constant is $\log(k_1/s^{-1}) = 13.78 - (48\,400 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}/2.303 \text{ RT})$. The decomposition of TMCBD leads exclusively to dimethylketene (DMK) whose buildup and subsequent decay were also followed kinetically. Studied at higher temperatures (450-520°), a first order decay constant of $\log(k_2/s^{-1}) = 10.72 - (48\,800 \text{ mol}^{-1}/2.303 \text{ RT})$ was determined for the thermal decomposition of DMK. Rates of decomposition of TMCBD and the corresponding cyclobutanone are compared and shown to be consistent with a twisted quasizwitterionic transition state. Long time (2 h) pyrolysis of TMCBD leads to tetramethylethylene and isopropenyl isopropyl ketone products but no DMK. These observations are rationalised by a scheme involving formation of tetramethylcyclopropanone (TMCP) from DMK and dimethylmethylene radicals, followed by decay of TMCP to the observed products.

THE thermolysis and photolysis of cyclobutanone and its alkylated derivatives have been the subjects of intense investigation^{1,2}. The photolysis of cyclobutanedione and its derivatives has also been much studied³⁻⁷, but little attention appears to have been given to the detailed study of the thermolysis of the cyclobutanediones. It has been of general knowledge⁸ for many years that the thermal decomposition of 1,3-cyclobutanedione (CBD) leads to ketene products, but the kinetics of the process and the presence of other decomposition pathways have not been reported. In this paper we present results on the kinetics and products of the thermolysis of tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione (TMCBD).

Three primary routes for *photolytic* decay have been proposed^{4,5} to account for the observations on TMCBD.

It has been shown⁴ that decomposition *via* the lowest triplet $n\pi^*$ state proceeds exclusively to dimethyl-

ketene (DMK, equation (3)), while decay *via* singlet $n\pi^*$ states yields tetramethylcyclopropanone (TMCP), CO (equation (2)) and DMK. The mechanism of production of tetramethylene (TME, equation (1)) is not completely understood but it appears not to be an important decomposition route⁴.

The purpose of the present investigation was to determine the primary thermal decomposition products and thermolysis kinetics for TMCBD. We were interested in determining whether both TMCP and DMK were formed (as in the singlet state photolysis) or whether DMK was the sole product (as in the triplet state sensitised photolysis), or whether other decomposition routes were active. Preliminary results on long time (~ 2 h) pyrolyses of gaseous samples, followed by product recuperation and mass spectrometric analysis, indicated that only TMCP and TME were formed. To verify this result FTIR was used to monitor, *in situ*, the thermolysis of TMCBD. These studies showed that DMK was formed exclusively, a result seemingly contradictory to our preliminary studies. Thermolysis decay constants for TMCBD disappearance were measured in the temperature range 383 to 430° and Arrhenius activation parameters determined. In addition, the thermal decomposition of the primary product DMK was followed kinetically in the range 450-520° and its activation parameters obtained.

Experimental

Preliminary studies: Small quantities (~ 1 g) of solid TMCBD (Eastman Kodak, recrystallised)

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

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were added to 20 cm long (2.0 cm ϕ) Pyrex tubes, attached to a vacuum line, evacuated and sealed off. The tubes were placed in a horizontal resistance-heated furnace and pyrolysed at 360° for 2 h. The tubes were opened in a glove-box under N_2 atmosphere and solvent (aniline or CCl_4) added. Gas chromatographic/mass spectrometric analyses were then performed on the solutions.

Reaction cell: A conventional 'static' vapor phase reaction cell was constructed from Pyrex tubing (25 \times 10 cm) wrapped with asbestos tape and nichrome wire (1.63 Ω /ft). The end windows (KBr, International Crystal, 50 mm ϕ) were attached to the cell *via* O-ring seals. The central portion of the cell was heated separately from the end portions to preclude excessive heating of the O-rings and sample condensation on the windows. The temperature of each of the three sections of the cell was monitored individually by thermocouples located in the insulation but in contact with the glass. A small radius cell was also utilised in some initial experiments with no effect on the rates observed. Cell pressures were monitored by a Wallace Tiernan pressure gauge.

Solid TMCBD was admitted to the reaction cell *via* a special greaseless Teflon-glass stopcock, the rotatable portion of which had been hollowed out to contain the sample. Inserted in an upright manner, the stopcock allowed the cell to be evacuated prior to sample introduction. Once the desired reaction temperature was stabilised the insert was rotated 180°, allowing the sample to drop into the cell, vaporise and commence decomposition. Aging of the cell was accomplished by repeated thermal decomposition runs with TMCBD itself. Reaction temperatures ranged between 380 and 520°.

Infrared spectrometer: The decomposition of TMCBD was followed spectroscopically using a Nicolet 7199 Fourier transform infrared spectrometer. The reaction cell was positioned between the main optical bench and the gc-ir optical bench with glass tubing (sealed to the outside of the KBr sample windows with O-rings) connecting each bench to the cell to preserve the integrity of the purge (liquid N_2 boil-off) in both optical benches. The light pipe was also purged and kept at ambient temperature. A HgCdTe (77 K) detector was used in the gc-ir bench. A spectrometer mirror velocity of 0.88 cm/s was used throughout; spectra of only 4 cm^{-1} resolution were collected to enable rapid collection sequences. Full aperture and the Happ-Genzel apodization function were utilised. The spectral range covered was 800-4 000 cm^{-1} , but only the 950-2 300 cm^{-1} region was examined in detail since the reactant and major products were known to have bands in this region.

Data acquisition and reduction: To monitor the thermal decomposition as a function of time with the FT-ir required that spectra be collected as rapidly as possible in the initial stages and less frequently as the reaction progressed. To accomplish

this, a set of macros was written that allows one to program the collection of spectra at different rates during the course of the process being monitored. The temporal resolution was limited by our optical arrangement and detector (MCT-type A) to about 20 single scan interferograms (4 cm^{-1} resolution, full spectral range) per minute. One can choose the four available 'time windows' for example as (W1) 20 spectra per min (1 scan each) for 5 min, followed by (W2) 2 spectra per min for 10 min, and so on for the remaining two time windows. Signal averaging is done (typically 10 scans/spectrum) in all but the fastest regime. Starting the data collection a few seconds prior to sample introduction allows monitoring the buildup of TMCBD as it is vaporised.

For the particular case of TMCBD pyrolysis, 65 interferograms were collected in W1, 20 spectra at 22 s intervals in W2, 10 spectra every 4 min in W3 and 10 spectra at 10 min intervals in W4. The choice of program may be changed depending on the temperature of the run. In this way one is able to monitor the relatively fast decay of the dione reactant and the much slower decomposition of the dimethyl ketene intermediate.

At the end of data collection another macro is started which converts each of the data files to absorbance spectra, relative to a background which was collected immediately prior to sample introduction. Integration of up to 4 regions is then performed (with base-line correction, if desired) and the results printed along with the time at which data collection was initiated. Two strong bands, at 2 133 cm^{-1} (CO stretch of DMK⁸) and at 1 755 cm^{-1} (antisymmetric CO stretch of the dione⁹) were chosen. While the integration of the former band was straightforward (limits of 2 185 to 1 990 cm^{-1}), the integration of the latter was complicated by the appearance of a broader weak band on its low frequency tail. This interference was avoided by integrating from the high frequency limit (1 830 cm^{-1}) to the band maximum (1 755 cm^{-1}) and multiplying by two. This was possible because of the symmetric band shape of the TMCBD carbonyl stretch, as determined in separate experiments. Absorption due to CO was seen at higher resolution (1 cm^{-1}). The P branch of the CO absorption superimposes on the DMK C=O stretch; however, it is weak and does not affect the results at 4 cm^{-1} resolution.

The integrated areas of the bands as a function of time were then fit *via* a linear least-squares program to suitable kinetic models and the rate constant for each temperature determined.

Results

Preliminary long-time pyrolysis: The gas chromatographic analysis of the decomposition product mixture showed three major peaks, two of which were readily identified by their mass spectro-

Fig. 1. Time evolution of the infrared band (1100-2300 cm^{-1} region) due to TMCBD decomposition (1755 cm^{-1}) and DMK buildup and decay (2133 cm^{-1}).

metric fragmentation patterns as undecomposed TMCBD parent and TME product. The third gc peak gave a parent mass peak of 112 and a fragmentation pattern which fits an isopropenyl isopropyl ketene (IPIPK) parent well.

Solution (CCl_4) infrared spectra were also run of the pyrolysed sample. No peak at 1840 cm^{-1} (from TMCP⁸) was observed but a band at 1810 cm^{-1} was apparent. Substituted vinyl groups are known¹⁰ to absorb in the $1750-1810 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. Thus, we conclude that the third gc peak is indeed due to the IPIPK product.

Decomposition rate constants: Fig. 1 shows the time evolution of a portion (first ~ 2 min) of the infrared spectra recorded. The band at 1755 cm^{-1} (TMCBD) clearly decreases with time, whereas the band at 2133 cm^{-1} (DMK) increases, reaches a maximum, and then decreases. No band at 1840 cm^{-1} (TMCP) was observed at any time¹¹. It may be noted that the first spectrum shown in Fig. 1 (at $t=0$) was not in fact the first recorded after introduction of the sample. A buildup of the TMCBD peak was observed due to its vaporisation; thus our determination of the decay kinetics was

not initiated until just after the TMCBD peak had reached a maximum. From these initial experiments the following mechanism was proposed,

where the products of DMK decomposition are probably CO and dimethylmethylene radical (*vide infra*). The third step was included for two reasons. First, our preliminary experiments indicated the presence of TMCP (or more accurately, IPIPK) in the long-time pyrolysis reaction mixture. And, second, Frey and Hopf¹ observed that thermolysis of the analogous mono-carbonyl compound, tetramethylcyclobutanone led to two pathways of decomposition. The major one leads to isobutene and DMK while the minor one yields tetramethylcyclopropane and CO. (We show later that the

third pathway above (*cf.* (3)) is not observed under our reaction condition.)

The three reaction steps (1)-(3), lead to the following integrated reaction rate expressions,

$$D(t) = D(O)e^{-(k_1+k_2)t} = D(O)e^{-k'_1 t} \quad (4)$$

$$K(t) = \frac{2k'_1 D(O)}{k'_1 - k_2} [e^{-k_2 t} - e^{-k'_1 t}] \quad (5)$$

where, $D(t)$ stands for TMCBD concentration at time t and $K(t)$ for DMK concentration at time t , and $k'_1 = k_1 + k_2$. Since our dependent variable is infrared absorbance and not concentration, the Beer's law expressions $A_D(t) = \epsilon_D D(t)$ and $A_K(t) = \epsilon_K K(t)$, where ϵ_D, ϵ_K are the molar absorptivities of TMCBD and DMK and l is the cell pathlength, were substituted into (4) and (5). For first order decomposition of TMCBD, plots of $\ln A_D(t)$ vs t should be linear. Indeed, good linear plots were found and from their slopes, values of $k'_1 (=k_1, \textit{vide infra})$ determined. They are given in Table 1 as a function of temperature for the

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS (k_1) FOR THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF TETRAMETHYLCYCLOBUTANEDIONE AS A FUNCTION OF TEMPERATURE

Temp. °C	$10^3 k_1/s^{-1}$
388	0.898
390	0.801
401	1.12
412	2.02
420	3.88
428	3.65
430	5.14

range 383-430°. Above $\sim 430^\circ$, the TMCBD decay times were too rapid to follow with the present technique.

From (5), it can be seen that if k'_1 either (i) becomes very large compared to k_2 (*e.g.* as at high temperatures), or (ii) the ketene concentrations are only sampled at long times (t very large, *i.e.* after the TMCBD concentration has dropped to essentially zero) this expression becomes (after the Beer's law substitutions),

$$A_K(t) = \frac{2A_D(O)k'_1}{k'_1 - k_2} \left(\frac{\epsilon_K}{\epsilon_D}\right) e^{-k_2 t} \quad (6)$$

Thus plots of $\ln A_K(t)$ vs t , should be linear with slopes equal to $-k_2$ and intercepts equal to $\frac{2A_D(O)k'_1 \epsilon_K}{(k'_1 - k_2) \epsilon_D}$. By using both long times and high temperatures, linear plots for the decomposition of DMK were found. The values determined for k_2 over the range 450-520° are given in Table 2. It may be noted that bands for both TMCBD and DMK decomposition were observed for the entire temperature range sampled (383-520°), but reliable kinetics for each were obtained only in the ranges quoted.

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS (k_2) FOR THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF DIMETHYLKETENE AS A FUNCTION OF TEMPERATURE

Temp. °C	$10^4 k_2/s^{-1}$
450	0.106
462	1.63
468	2.06
480	3.25
490	5.12
500	8.80
520	20.09

It is of interest to determine the relative magnitudes of the extinction coefficients for the dione and the ketene. It can be seen, from (6), that the intercept of the plot of $\ln A_K(t)$ vs t contains the desired ratio. The quantities $A_D(O)$ and k'_1 were found from the TMCBD decay, while k_2 was determined from the DMK decay. The results obtained for ϵ_K/ϵ_D are shown in Table 3. The values should of course be constant with temperature. The average is $1.3 \pm 0.2 (\pm \sigma)$.

TABLE 3—RATIO OF EXTINCTION COEFFICIENTS (ϵ_K/ϵ_D) FOR THE DMK 2 193 cm^{-1} BAND AND THE TMCBD 1 755 cm^{-1} BAND

Temp. °C	ϵ_K/ϵ_D
388	1.26
390	1.085
401	1.22
412	1.34
420	1.55
428	1.35
430	1.57
450	1.67

Arrhenius parameters: Arrhenius plots for the data contained in Tables 1 and 2 are shown in Fig. 2. The Arrhenius equations describing these plots are given by

$$\log [k_1/s^{-1}] = 13.78 - (48\,400 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}/2.303 \text{ RT})$$

for the decomposition of TMCBD and

$$\log [k_2/s^{-1}] = 10.72 - (48\,800 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}/2.303 \text{ RT})$$

for the decomposition of DMK.

We have stated above that at no time in the vapor phase ir studies did we observe an infrared band at 1 840 cm^{-1} which would have indicated the presence of TMCP as a decomposition product. With the estimated lower limit^{1,4} for TMCP of $\epsilon \sim 2.0 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ about equal to the ϵ_{CO} for DMK⁵, we estimate that if 5% or more of the decomposition of TMCBD had occurred *via* the TMCP pathway we could have observed it. A confirmation of the relative unimportance of this route can be gotten from the Arrhenius plots. If we assume for the moment that both k_1 and k_2 routes are important in the TMCBD decomposition, each

Fig. 2. Arrhenius plots for thermal decomposition of TMCBD (upper and right axes) and DMK (lower and left axes). Data from Tables 1 and 2.

rate will be described by its own Arrhenius equation and the observed rate by

$$k'_1 = k_1 + k_s = A_1 e^{-\Delta E_1/kt} + A_s e^{-\Delta E_s/kt}$$

Plotting $\ln k'_1$ vs T^{-1} will yield non-linear plots. However, if $k_1 \gg k_s$, plots of $\ln k'_1$ vs T^{-1} will be linear. Since we observe a good linear plot of $\ln k_1$ vs T^{-1} (cf. Fig. 2) this confirms that the k_s route to TMCP is much slower (if not zero) compared to the k_1 route to DMK.

Discussion

TMCBD decomposition: From our results we have demonstrated that the only primary thermal decomposition product of TMCBD is DMK. The decay of TMCBD was followed spectroscopically in the IR simultaneously with the buildup and decay of DMK. No other major decomposition products from TMCBD were noted, although because of the low pressures used, trace amounts (< 5%) of other products could have been produced but not observed. If we accept that DMK is the sole primary thermolysis product, how can the appearance of isopropenylisopropylketone and tetramethylethylene in our long time pyrolysis studies be understood? The most likely explanation seems to be that with such long pyrolysis times secondary reactions are occurring. We suggest the following scheme

Pathways (4) and (5) have previously been proposed by Haller and Srinivasan⁷ as an alternate route for formation of the TMCP observed in photolysis decomposition products. Pathway (7) has been shown by Turro and coworkers⁸ to occur upon heating in the vapor phase chromatographic analysis of a crude photolysis decomposition mixture. (The dimerisation of DMK to TMCBD is slow^{13,14} and only becomes significant at pressures above 1 atm, so is of no importance here.) In this scheme the formation of TMCP is a bimolecular one but since the decomposition of TMCBD is fast relative to DMK, a large excess of DMK will be present in the reaction cell as the dimethylmethylene is formed. Thus the TMCP formation reaction will become increasingly more probable as the TMCBD and DMK decay reactions proceed. An alternate route to the TME product (instead of (6)) could be the bimolecular reaction of two dimethylmethylene radicals. This is considered less likely given the expected excess of DMK in the cell which will react with the dimethylmethylene to form TMCP and given the fact that both TME and IPIPK were observed to be major long-time pyrolysis products. In summary, it appears reasonable to conclude that the appearance of TME and IPIPK in our long-time thermolysis mixture results from secondary reactions occurring after the primary decay of TMCBD to DMK.

It is of interest to determine the effect on the reaction rate and activation energy of the addition of a carbonyl group to the cyclobutanone moiety. Frey and Hopf¹ have measured the thermolysis rate constant of 2,2,4,4-tetramethylcyclobutanone to be $\log k_1 = 14.859 - (55\,945 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}/2.303 \text{ RT})$ for the major decomposition pathway to isobutene and DMK. For the minor (6%) pathway to tetramethylcyclopropane and CO, they found a similar though less favored rate, $\log k_s = 14.867 - (59\,587 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}/2.303 \text{ RT})$. The rate for the decomposition of TMCBD found here is $\log k = 13.78 - (48\,400 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}/2.303 \text{ RT})$. Evaluating these rates at 400° (the middle of our range), the TMCBD decay rate constant is a factor of ~25 greater than the rate for the mono-ketone decay. This is an understandable rate increase within the twisted quasizwitterionic transition state model previously proposed by Frey¹⁵ and Egger¹⁶ for the thermal decomposition of cyclobutanes and cyclobutanones. A twisted transition state was suggested by Frey and co-worker¹⁵ to account for the effects of alkyl substituents in cyclobutane systems in an attempt to incorporate some of the ideas of orbital symmetry conservation into the problem. In this model, alkyl substituents on nonadjacent ring positions are expected to interfere sterically in the twisted transition state model and hence to decrease the rate of decomposition. The slower rate of decomposition of 2,2,4,4-tetramethylcyclobutanone compared to cyclobutanone is thus perfectly rationalised within this model. Egger¹⁶ further suggested that there is a charge separation in the twisted transition state of cyclobutanones which becomes zwitterionic-like and

leads to larger decay rates for substituents in the 3-position than in the 2- or 4-positions. Within this model then we would expect that substitution of a carbonyl group in the 3-position of 2,2,4,4-tetramethylcyclobutanone would lead to an enhanced rate of decomposition for TMCBD. This is of course just what we observe. Similarly, a comparison of 1,3-cyclobutanedione (CBD) stability to TMCBD stability is predictable within this model. Since the major influence of the transannular methyl groups in TMCBD is a steric one tending to constrain the transition state geometry, the expectation is that the TMCBD should decompose more slowly than CBD. Although no kinetic data are available for CBD thermolysis, one report on its infrared spectroscopy remarks that it is an unstable compound¹⁷. On the other hand, TMCBD is known to be a relatively stable molecule.

DMK decomposition: The investigation of the kinetics of decomposition of the parent ketene has undergone an interesting evolution. In 1958, Young¹⁸ studied the decomposition of ketene in the 780-860 K (100 torr) range and found that the reaction order was 2. Ten years later, Huda and Kuratani¹⁹ used shock tube methods with a 1140-1530 K temperature range to study ketene's decay and found a reaction order of 1.5. Then, in 1971, Wagner and Zabel²⁰ also using shock tube methods (in the temperature range 1300-2000 K) determined the ketene decay reaction order to be 1 and the rate constant to be $k = 3.6 \times 10^{12} \exp(-59300 \pm 2000 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}/RT) \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Although not directly measured the latter measurement implied that the primary decomposition products were methylene radical and CO. To prove this point, Reineke and Strein²¹ in an elegant molecular beam experiment expanded a gas mixture of ketene decomposition products and argon into a vacuum and mass spectrometrically analysed for the methylene species. Their measured ionisation potential is in excellent agreement with the spectroscopic value determined earlier by Herzberg²².

In the result presented here no attempt was made to determine the reaction order. The detection of the dimethylmethylene radical in the ir would have been difficult if not impossible given the other species present in the reaction cell or produced from the TMCBD decomposition. As mentioned previously, CO was observed, its bands lying on the low frequency edge of the TMCBD carbonyl stretch. They could however not be used for quantitative measurement since they were resolution limited. A single run at 0.25 cm^{-1} revealed their vibrational/rotational pattern clearly. Nevertheless, the similarities in the reaction rates of the parent ketene and the dimethylated compound ($k_{\text{DMK}}/k_{\text{KET}} \sim 17$ at 475°)

supports the conclusion made in the previous section that the primary decomposition route in DMK is to the dimethylmethylene radical and CO.

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